

A Study on Synthetic Humic Acids

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Three different samples of humic acids were synthesised from hydroquinone and three different amino acids by means of alkaline oxidation with potassium peroxodisulphate. The synthetic acids have been characterised by electrometric (potentiometry) titrations, viscosity, surface tension, visible and infrared spectral data with a view to probe their physicochemical properties. The results have been correlated with coiling-decoiling behaviour as well as aliphatic-aromatic balance of the acids. Attempts have also been made to obtain semiquantitative information on the shape and dimensions of these synthetic products from the corresponding parameters as above.

'SYNTHETIC humic acids' are synthetic analogues of natural humic acids and provide useful materials for studying the properties of the latter which are of rather complex molecular nature. Thus, these natural polymeric acids can not be split into definite fractions by usual degradation techniques unlike the proteins and polysaccharides, and often pose serious problem for characterisation. The principal features of humic acids—the polyelectrolytic behaviour and three-dimensional structures—are probed in details in the present paper by looking at different properties of some synthetic humic acids bearing resemblance to the natural products.

The experiments conducted for the purpose involved the electrometric titrations, viscometric, surface tension, visible and infrared spectral measurements.

Experimental

Humic acids were synthesised by the alkaline oxidation of α -amino acids and hydroquinone using potassium peroxodisulphate as the oxidising agent¹. The synthetic acids were denoted as follows (starting materials in parenthesis): HA₁ (α -alanine and hydroquinone), HA₂ (glycine and hydroquinone), and HA₃ (histidine and hydroquinone).

Potentiometric titration: Potentiometric titrations were carried out by using standard NaOH solution. Carboxylic and phenolic-OH group contents were reckoned from the acidity equivalents of the initial and final inflexion points of titration curves². The amount of fresh alkali needed to attain a stable higher pH, following a fall in the final pH (on standing after initial titration), as well as the time required for the same were also recorded for each sample.

Viscosity measurements: The viscosities of HA suspensions were measured (while rendering all the COOH groups to sodium carboxylate form over a concentration range of 0.01–0.1% by the use of a

Ubbelohde viscometer having an average flow time of 409.4 s for 11 ml of distilled water at 26°. The *A* and *B* coefficients of the Jones-Doles equation were obtained from the intercept and slope of the best-fit linear plot of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} , according to the relation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\sqrt{C}} - \frac{\eta_0}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (1)$$

where, η and η_0 denote the respective viscosities of the HA suspension having a percent concentration *C* and water, and *A* and *B* the empirical constants. The B_{expt} value of the humate anion was then obtained by subtracting the literature value³ of B_{Na^+} from B_{expt} value of sodium humate,

$$B_{\text{expt}} = B_{\text{Na-HA}} - B_{\text{Na}^+}$$

The B_{expt} values were approximated to the respective intrinsic viscosities⁴, $[\eta]$ which were used to compute the molecular weight (*M*) from the modified Staudinger equation⁵,

$$[\eta] = K(M)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

where, $K = 7.3 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\alpha = 0.65$.

The polyelectrolytic behaviour of the HA samples was ascertained by plotting the corresponding (η_{sp}/C) values against *C*. A representative plot (for HA₃) is give in Fig. 1.

The partial molar volume (\bar{V}) for the polymeric acids was ascertained (at a concentration of 0.03%) by fitting the density data of aqueous HA suspensions to the equation⁶,

$$\bar{V} = \frac{M}{1000 \left[\rho - \frac{d\rho}{dC} \times C \right]} \quad (3)$$

where, *C* is molar concentration of the HA suspension, ρ the density of the suspension at concentration *C* and $d\rho/dC$ the slope of ρ vs *C* plots at *C* (i.e., 0.03%).

Surface tension measurements: Surface tension of aqua-humic acids at various concentrations was

 Fig. 1. Variation of η_{sp}/C vs C for HA_3 sample.

measured with the help of a du Nouy's tensiometer at a constant temperature of 26° maintaining pH of the solution at 8.0. The experiments were then repeated by taking the given humic acids in a 0.1 M NaCl solution. The surface excess, τ , was computed for both aqua-humic acids and those in presence of 0.1 M NaCl, by using the slope $d\gamma/dC$ of the γ vs C plots in the Gibbs absorption equation⁷,

$$\tau = -\frac{1}{RT} \cdot C \cdot \frac{d\gamma}{dC} \quad (4)$$

Visible and ir spectra : The optical densities at 465 nm and 665 nm for the humic acid solution (Na-form) were noted with the help of a Systronix spectrophotometer at two different pH 7.0 and 9.0.

Ir spectra (KBr) HA of samples were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer fitted with a NaCl prism.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometry : The carboxylic and phenolic-OH contents were computed from the acidity equivalents

of the first and final inflexion points of the potentiometric curves and also a pH difference, namely, $\Delta pH = pH_{3/4} - pH_{1/4}$, are recorded in Table 1, where $pH_{1/4}$ and $pH_{3/4}$ refer to pH values corresponding to one-fourth and three-fourths of the final inflexion points. pH values of the HA samples are > 0.954 which signifies the polyprotic nature of the given acid samples⁸.

The amount of fresh alkali needed to attain a stable higher pH (when HA molecules were completely unfolded) evidently depends on the amount of the remainder H^+ ions which are not accessible to alkali. This, in turn, is governed by the steric hindrance associated with a particular conformation of the molecules due to their coiled shape. Again, the time required to attain a stable higher pH depends on the ease of decoiling which is inversely related to the intramolecular H-bonding. Formation of such hydrogen bonds is often interrupted by the R group of the amino acid unit. For instance, HA_1 containing a larger R group than HA_3 , requires a comparatively shorter time and a smaller amount of fresh alkali for attaining the stable higher pH (Table 2). HA_3 behaves somewhat differently in requiring a very small amount of excess alkali, but a fairly long time is required to attain the final stable pH. This could possibly be attributed to the presence of an additional heterocyclic ring in the side-chain of the corresponding amino acid component (histidine), which may render the structure of HA_3 largely coiled because of entropy considerations⁹. Such coil formation thus does not necessitate the participation of the carboxylic and phenolic-OH groups in intramolecular hydrogen bond formation and hence not much 'excess acidity' gets locked inside the coils.

Viscometry : Table 3 records the experimental B values of the HA samples. For a given component, hydroquinone, the humic acid synthesised from glycine (HA_3) shows a higher B_{opt} value than the acid sample synthesised from alanine (HA_1). While the additional methyl group of alanine

TABLE 1—POTENTIOMETRIC INFORMATION ABOUT HA

HA sample*	Amount of COOH meq g ⁻¹	Amount of PhOH meq g ⁻¹	pH at first inflexion (pH ₁)	pH at final inflexion (pH ₃)	ΔpH^{**} $pH_{3/4} - pH_{1/4}$	Conclusion
HA_1	2.30	5.096	8.10	9.80	4.90	Polyprotic
HA_2	3.95	2.561	8.55	9.90	4.95	Polyprotic
HA_3	0.744	2.149	5.45	8.65	4.80	Polyprotic

*Conclusion : all samples are polyprotic. ** $(pH_{3/4} - pH_{1/4})$.

TABLE 2—AMOUNT OF FRESH ALKALI AND TIME REQUIRED TO ATTAIN A STABLE pH

HA sample	Amount of fresh alkali required to attain stable pH meq g ⁻¹	Time required to attain stable pH h
HA_1	18.10	26.5
HA_2	17.86	46.5
HA_3	1.24	24.5

TABLE 3—*B* COEFFICIENT, INTRINSIC VISCOSITY, MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND PARTIAL MOLAR VOLUME OF HA SAMPLES

HA sample	B_{expt} of Na-humate (percent ⁻¹) $B_{\text{HA-Na}}$	B_{expt} of humate anion/percent ⁻¹ ($B_{\text{expt}} = B_{\text{HA-Na}} - B_{\text{Na}^+}$)	Mol. wt.	Partial molar volume (\bar{V})** cm ³ mol ⁻¹
HA ₁	0.392 8	0.355 5	13 629	18.7
HA ₂	0.452 9	0.415 6	17 831	17.4
HA ₃	0.450 9	0.413 6	17 203	17.2

* B_{Na^+} value from Ref. 3. ** \bar{V} values refer to a concentration of 0.03 %.

TABLE 4—SURFACE TENSION AND SURFACE EXCESS OF HA SAMPLES AT 25°

HA sample	<i>C</i> %	Surface tension in presence of water (γ') dyne cm ⁻¹	Surface tension in presence of salt (γ') dyne cm ⁻¹	Surface excess in presence of water (τ) × 10 ¹⁰ × 10 ¹⁰ mol cm ⁻²	Surface excess in presence of 0.1 M NaCl (τ') × 10 ¹⁰ mol cm ⁻²
HA ₁	0.011 8	63.3	57.0	0.19	3.86
	0.021 6	63.1	53.9		
	0.030 0	63.0	51.2		
HA ₂	0.007 8	63.5	63.0	0.17	0.63
	0.014 3	63.4	62.8		
	0.019 8	63.3	62.5		
HA ₃	0.021 0	64.8	—	0.18	—
	0.038 0	64.6	—		
	0.066 6	64.3	—		

component in HA₁ would tend to lead to higher micro-viscosity than for HA₂, due to reinforcement of H-bonded 'local' structure in water through hydrophobic hydration effect⁹; a higher 'coiled-character' of HA₂, referred to above, would cause an opposite trend because of 'obstruction effect'¹⁰. The effect of these two reverse tendencies tends to result in a slightly higher *B* coefficient for HA₂. In case of HA₃, exhibiting a similar *B* value as HA₂, the determining factor also appears to be the 'obstruction effect'.

A typical hyperbolic nature of variation of (η_{sp}/C) against *C* (Fig. 1) was observed to characterise each HA sample, thereby signifying the polyelectrolytic nature. A greater partial molar volume for HA₂ (with higher [η] value) appears to be associated with a larger cavity needed to hold the sample in aqueous medium as compared to HA₁. The HA₃ sample behaves similarly as HA₂.

Surface excess: The τ value (surface excess) is an index of hydrophobicity. The latter, in turn, depends on the nature of the aliphatic and aromatic moiety of the synthetic acids. Thus, for the same phenolic unit, hydroquinone HA₁, synthesised from a C₂-amino acid, exhibited a greater τ value than HA₂, synthesised from a C₃-amino acid (Table 4). A rather low τ for HA₃, on the other hand, probably arises from the presence of a closed ring structure in histidine component of HA₃ which tends to reduce its hydrophobic influence. This gets qualitative support from a reported lower entropy loss accompanying the transfer of cyclic ethers and amines from gas phase (at 1 atm pressure) to dilute aqueous solutions as compared to their open chain analogues¹¹. A sharp rise in τ , especially so for

HA₁, in aqueous solution of 0.1 M NaCl obviously results from a higher degree of 'exclusion' of the predominantly hydrophobic humic acids in presence of the strongly hydrated electrolyte.

Spectrophotometry: Table 5 records the E_a/E_b values of the HA samples. These being all greater than unity show that the absorbance by the aliphatic part (i.e. absorbance at 465 nm) is greater than that by the aromatic part (i.e. absorbance at 665 nm) due to a particular conformational arrangement of the aliphatic and the aromatic moiety.

TABLE 5—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF HA SAMPLES

HA sample	E_a/E_b at pH		$\Delta(E_a/E_b)$
	7.0	9.0	
HA ₁	1.807 6	1.436 9	0.370 7
HA ₂	4.147 5	3.955 6	0.191 9
HA ₃	2.912 7	2.533 8	0.378 9

Table 5 also records the $\Delta(E_a/E_b)$ ratio, namely, $\Delta(E_a/E_b) = (E_a/E_b)$ at pH 7.0 minus (E_a/E_b) at pH 9.0. The latter may be taken as an 'index of flexibility' of the HA molecules owing to the fact that addition of alkali (NaOH) rendered HA molecules 'unfolded under thermodynamic compulsion'¹². This leads to the destruction of the tertiary structures (i.e. three-dimensional configuration) of the molecules, thereby resulting in changes in the above absorbance ratios. However, such unfolding is disfavoured by the intramolecular H-bonding, the ease of which depends on the size of R group of the component amino acid as well as the solubility of the component phenolic unit. For instance, with the same phenolic unit, hydroquinone, a higher

TABLE 6—IR SPECTRAL DATA FOR HA SAMPLES

HA ₁	HA ₂	HA ₃	Remarks
3 560-3 100s, b 1 720w	3 600-3 200s, b 1 700w	3 600-3 000s, b 1 720w	H-bonded Ph-OH, partly N-H stretch of free NH ₂ C=O stretch of amides
1 610-1 580m, b	1 620-1 590m, b	1 620-1 550m, b	C=O stretch of arom. ketones, COOH and C=O stretch of aromatic rings
1 510-1 440w, b			C=O stretch of arom. rings, C-H bend of aliph. OH ₂
1 400w	1 400-1 380w	1 400-1 350w	C-H bend of aliph. OH ₂ and COO ⁻ stretch
1 220-1 180m, b	1 240-1 200w, b	1 200-1 180m, b	C-N stretch of amide (arom. or aliph.) and C=O (stretch of alcohols)

$\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ is observed for HA₁ than for HA₂ due presumably to the presence of an additional methyl group in alanine. With HA₃, a somewhat lower $\Delta(E_4/E_6)$ is observed than that for HA₁ and is probably associated with a lower hydrophobic character of histidine, referred to above, as compared to alanine, both being essentially 3-carbon amino acids.

The ir spectral data (Table 6) show that the HA samples contain more or less identical functional groups, like phenolic-OH, CONH₂, CH₃, free NH and COOH (as COO⁻ anion). The absorption band at 1 600 cm⁻¹ registers that these HA molecules are well-aromatised which is in agreement with the earlier reports^{2,11}.

Semiquantitative information on shape and dimension of the humic acids: A methodology is proposed here to arrive at an idea about the size and shape of the given HA samples. Thus, the Einstein equation of viscosity reads,

$$\eta_{sp} = k\phi = kC\bar{V} \quad (5)$$

where, η_{sp} is the specific viscosity of the suspension and k a constant dependent on the shape of the dispersed phase particles (for spherical particles, $k=2.5$, while for rod or disc shaped particles, $k>2.5$), ϕ the volume fraction occupied by the dispersed phase particles, C the molar concentration of the dispersed phase particles, and \bar{V} the corresponding partial molar volume. An appropriate substitution of η_{sp} , \bar{V} and C in equation (5) lead to the evaluation of k . These values (Table 7) were

 TABLE 7— k VALUES OF EQUATION (5) AND AXIAL RATIOS OF HA SAMPLES

HA samples	k	τ $\times 10^{10}$ cm ⁻¹	h/r $\times 10^{-4}$
HA ₁	24.2	2.59	4.16
HA ₂	40.6	2.95	10.69
HA ₃	44.8	2.28	18.51

found to be much greater than 2.5, indicating that the given HA molecules are highly non-spherical.

Calculations of axial ratios of the HA molecules: Considering HA molecules as open cylinders, the volume of a single molecule is given by \bar{V}/N , where N is the Avogadro number, and half of the external curved surface area is given by $\pi r h$ (where, r is the radius of the particle and h its length).

$$\text{Evidently, } \pi r^2 h = \bar{V}/N \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and } \pi r h = 1/N\tau \quad (8)$$

where, τ is the surface excess of the HA sample. The underlying assumption is that the HA molecules at the surface are only 'half-immersed' because of their predominantly hydrophobic character. The value of r and h were next obtained by solving equations (7) and (8). The axial ratios (h/r) of the HA samples were computed and are recorded in Table 7.

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